

A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Role of Androgen Receptor Expression in Triple Negative Breast Cancer

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Abstract

Background: According to WHO In 2022, an estimated 2.3 million new cases of breast cancer were diagnosed among women globally, along with around 670,000 deaths. The WHO Global Breast Cancer Initiative highlights that TNBC contributes significantly to inequities especially because of its frequency in lower-income countries and impacts on younger women. Triple-Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC) is an aggressive subtype of breast cancer characterized by the lack of estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor, and HER2 expression and constitutes approximately 15–20% of all breast cancers. It is associated with poor prognosis, early recurrence, and limited treatment options.

Objective: To systematically review and quantitatively synthesize existing evidence on the association between AR expression and survival outcomes Disease-Free Survival and overall survival in patients with TNBC.

Methods: A comprehensive literature search was conducted across PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus databases for studies published from January 2010 to December 2019. Eligible studies included histologically confirmed TNBC patients, with reported AR status and survival outcomes (OS and/or DFS). Pooled Hazard Ratios and 95% Confidence Intervals were calculated using a random-effects model. Heterogeneity was assessed using I^2 statistics. Subgroup analyses were performed based on AR and ER cut-offs and geographic regions. Publication bias was evaluated using funnel plots and Egger's test.

Results: A total of 13 studies from diverse geographical locations were published between 2010 and 2019. The Random Effects model pooled estimate is 0.49 [95% CI: 0.34, 0.65] and Forest plot demonstrated a significant positive effect of AR expression on DFS. Subgroup analysis indicated no significant heterogeneity in DFS based on AR ($p = 0.8366$) or ER cut-offs ($p = 0.4002$), but a statistically significant difference was observed across geographic regions ($p = 0.0223$). Funnel plot assessing no publication bias was found for DFS (Egger's $p = 0.06$), while bias was present for OS (Egger's $p = 0.0346$).

Conclusion: This review lays a strong foundation for future research to better understand the potential role of AR in guiding treatment and understanding the progression of TNBC.

Keywords: Triple-negative breast cancer, Androgen receptor, Disease-free survival, Overall survival, Meta-analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the most common cancer affecting women worldwide, with 2.3 million new diagnoses and 685,000 fatalities in 2020, making it the leading cause of cancer mortality in women globally [1]. Among the subtypes, Triple-Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC) makes up roughly 15–20% of all breast cancer cases and is distinguished by its absence of Estrogen receptor (ER), Progesterone receptor (PR), and Human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) expression [2]-[3]. TNBC is an aggressive subtype associated with early recurrence, high rates of metastasis, and poor overall survival compared to other subtypes [4]. The incidence of TNBC is disproportionately higher among younger women, premenopausal women, and those of African or Hispanic descent [5]-[6]. The disease burden is further exacerbated by its heterogeneous nature, lack of targeted therapies, and limited treatment options, making it a major public health challenge [7].

Risk factors for TNBC include both modifiable and non-modifiable elements. Genetic mutations, particularly in the BRCA1 gene, are strongly associated with TNBC [8]. Other risk factors include high breast density, early menarche, late menopause, obesity, nulliparity, and a family history of breast or ovarian cancer [9]-[10]. Clinical presentation of TNBC is often similar to other breast cancer types but tends to progress more rapidly. Symptoms commonly include a palpable mass, breast pain, nipple retraction, skin changes (such as dimpling or redness), and in some cases, axillary lymphadenopathy [11]. However, due to its aggressive biology, TNBC often presents at a more advanced stage and has a higher likelihood of visceral metastasis, especially to the lungs and brain [12].

Treatment for TNBC remains challenging due to the lack of hormone receptors and HER2 expression. Standard treatment regimens primarily rely on surgery, radiation, and cytotoxic chemotherapy, including anthracyclines, taxanes, and platinum agents [13]. Despite being initially chemo sensitive, TNBC patients frequently experience relapse within three years of diagnosis [14]. Recently, immune checkpoint inhibitors (e.g., atezolizumab and pembrolizumab) and poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) inhibitors (e.g., olaparib) have demonstrated some efficacy, particularly in patients with PD-L1 expression or BRCA mutations [15]-[16].

Prevention strategies for TNBC include lifestyle modification, such as maintaining a healthy body weight, regular physical activity, avoiding alcohol consumption, and breastfeeding [17]. For high-risk individuals, especially BRCA1/2 mutation carriers, risk-reducing strategies such as prophylactic mastectomy and salpingo-oophorectomy may significantly reduce the risk of TNBC [18]. Given the lack of hormone receptors in TNBC, researchers have been exploring alternative molecular targets, and one such emerging biomarker is the androgen receptor (AR). Although traditionally associated with prostate cancer, AR is expressed in a subset of TNBCs and has been proposed to play a potential role in tumor progression and therapeutic targeting [19]. Understanding the prognostic value and predictive role of AR in TNBC could guide personalized treatment strategies and improve clinical outcomes.

Therefore, this systematic review and meta-analysis aims to assess the association between androgen receptor expression and survival outcomes—Disease-Free Survival (DFS) and Overall Survival (OS) in patients with TNBC, integrating findings from diverse global populations.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Search Strategy

A thorough literature search was conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines [20]. Databases including PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus—were systematically explored for studies published between January 2010 and December 2019. The search strategy incorporated keywords and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms such as "*Androgen Receptor*," "*Overall Survival*," "*Disease-Free Survival*," "*Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy*," "*Triple Negative Breast Cancer*," and "*Breast Cancer*," combined using Boolean operators to optimize study retrieval. Furthermore, manual searches of reference lists from selected articles and relevant systematic reviews were performed to identify additional eligible studies.

B. Eligibility Criteria

The inclusion criteria for studies were as follows: (1) publication as a full-length article in a peer-reviewed journal, encompassing prospective or retrospective cohort studies, case-control studies, and randomized controlled trials; (2) enrolment of patients with histologically confirmed Triple-Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC); and (3) comparative studies reporting all three outcomes—Disease-Free Survival (DFS), Overall Survival (OS), and androgen receptor (AR) status in relation to outcomes. Studies were excluded if they (1) lacked clearly defined clinical outcomes, (2) were narrative reviews, duplicate publications, or editorials, or (3) were published in languages other than English.

C. Data Extraction

Two independent reviewers systematically evaluated all retrieved titles and abstracts, subsequently assessing full-text articles for final inclusion according to the predetermined eligibility criteria. Using a standardized data collection form, the following information was extracted from each selected study: first author's name, publication year, country of origin, sample size (n), methods, Androgen Receptor (AR) status, cut-off values for Estrogen Receptor (ER) and AR, number of AR-positive patients,

survival endpoints (either Overall Survival (OS), Disease-Free Survival (DFS), or both), and the reported Hazard Ratio (HR) with the corresponding 95% confidence interval (CI).

D. Statistical Analysis

The study primarily assessed OS and DFS by comparing AR expression in TNBC cases. Pooled hazard ratios (HRs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were computed using a random-effects model (DerSimonian and Laird method) to address between-study variability. Study heterogeneity was evaluated through Cochran's Q test and I² statistics, where I² values exceeding 50% indicated significant heterogeneity. To investigate heterogeneity sources, subgroup analyses were conducted based on AR detection thresholds (low vs. high cut-off), ER cut-off values (low vs. high vs. not applicable), and geographic region (Europe vs. Asia vs. North America). Publication bias was assessed both visually through funnel plots and statistically using Egger's regression test, with a p-value <0.05 considered statistically significant for all analyses. All meta-analytical procedures were performed using R programming language version 4.2.2.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Studies retrieved and characteristics

A total of 1,257 articles were initially identified. After removing duplicates, 890 articles remained. Following the exclusion of 804 irrelevant articles based on title and abstract screening, 86 articles were selected for full-text review. Of these, 73 were excluded after detailed evaluation, resulting in 13 studies that met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final analysis, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 PRISMA Flow Diagram of included studies

The table I summarizes the characteristics of studies included in a meta-analysis assessing the prognostic significance of Androgen Receptor expression in TNBC patients. A total of 13 studies from diverse geographical locations including Italy, Korea, China, Singapore, Japan, the USA, and Greece were published between 2010 and 2019, with sample sizes ranging from 81 to 1467 patients.

The most commonly used method for AR detection was Immunohistochemistry (IHC), applied either directly or on Tissue Microarrays (TMA). AR positivity cut-offs varied across studies, such as 1% of cells showing staining, while others used higher thresholds like 10%, 75%, or scoring systems like the Allred score. These differences affected the AR positivity rates, which varied widely from as low as 17.7% to as high as 78.6%. Most of the studies looked at patient outcomes such as OS, DFS, or both, to find if AR expression had any relationship with prognosis. The ER cut-off values across studies ranged from >1% to ≥10%. This variability highlights the lack of standardization, potentially affecting comparability and clinical interpretation.

TABLE I

CHARACTERISTICS OF INCLUDED STUDIES EVALUATING AR EXPRESSION IN TNBC

Name	Country	Year	n	Methods	AR Cut-off	AR +ve n(%)	Outcomes	ER cut-off
Castellano I et al ^[21]	Italy	2010	859	IHC on TMA	$\geq 1\%$ Literature based	609 (70.8%)	OS+DFS	$>1\%$ of cells
Park S et al ^[22]	Korea	2011	931	IHC on TMA	$\geq 10\%$ arbitrary	541 (58.1%)	OS+DFS	$\geq 10\%$ of cells
Yu Q et al ^[23]	China	2011	327	IHC	>1 Allred Score (Intensity X %)	237 (72.4%)	DFS	$>1\%$ of cells
Pistelli M et al ^[24]	Italy	2014	81	IHC	$\geq 10\%$ nuclear staining arbitrarily	15 (18.5%)	OS+DFS	$\geq 10\%$ of cells
He J et al ^[25]	China	2012	287	IHC on TMA	$\geq 5\%$ nuclear staining arbitrarily	74 (25.7%)	DFS	NA
Thike AA et al ^[26]	Singapore	2013	679	IHC on TMA	$\geq 1\%$ nuclear staining literature based	267 (38.1%)	OS+DFS	$>1\%$ of cells
Tokunaga E et al ^[27]	Japan	2013	250	IHC	75% nuclear staining literature based	155 (62%)	DFS	$\geq 1\%$ of cells
Hu R et al ^[28]	USA	2012	1467	IHC on TMA	$>1\%$ arbitrary	1154 (78.6%)	OS	NA
Choi JE et al ^[29]	Korea	2015	492	IHC	1%	87 (17.7%)	OS+DFS	1%
Luo X et al ^[30]	China	2010	137	IHC	IHC score ≥ 2	38 (27.7%)	OS+DFS	NA
McGhan LJ et al ^[31]	USA	2014	94	IHC	10%	22 (23.0%)	OS	NA
Giannos A et al ^[32]	Greece	2015	90	IHC	Allred score 1	45 (50%)	OS	NA
Dieci MV et al ^[33]	Italy	2019	263	IHC	1%	78 (27%)	OS	10%

B. Disease Free Survival (DFS)

A total of nine studies reported pooled estimate under the Random-Effects (RE) model demonstrated a significant positive effect of AR expression on DFS shown in figure 2. The RE model pooled estimate is 0.49 [95% CI: 0.34, 0.65], which suggests a statistically significant overall positive effect across studies. Notably, there was significant heterogeneity among the included studies ($I^2 = 59.67\%$, $p = 0.0085$; $\text{Tau}^2 = 0.026$; $Q = 20.54$), indicating moderate to substantial variability in effect sizes.

Fig. 2 Forest plot for impact of Androgen Receptor expression on DFS

C. Subgroup analysis of DFS

The subgroup analysis assessed whether AR cut-off, ER cut-off, or region significantly contributed to heterogeneity in the pooled hazard ratios. AR cut-off ($p = 0.8366$) and ER cut-off ($p = 0.4002$) showed no statistically significant effect, suggesting that variation in cut-off thresholds for these receptors did not significantly influence survival outcomes across studies. However, the analysis revealed a statistically significant geographic variation ($p=0.0223$), with European studies showing a stronger protective effect (HR = 0.27, 95% CI: 0.09–0.44; $I^2 = 0\%$) compared to Asian studies (HR = 0.53, 95% CI: 0.38–0.69; $I^2 = 57\%$). This suggests that regional factors may influence the prognostic impact, potentially due to variations in population characteristics, clinical practices, or biomarker assessment methods.

TABLE II

SUBGROUP ANALYSIS OF AR EXPRESSION ON DFS BY CUT-OFF THRESHOLDS AND GEOGRAPHIC REGIONS

Variables	N	I squared(%)	HR	95% CI	p-value
AR Cutoff					0.8366
Low Cutoff	6	71.5	0.4911	0.279-0.702	
High Cutoff	3	15	0.5243	0.289-0.759	
ER Cutoff					0.4002
Low Cutoff	5	77.2	0.5054	0.272-0.738	
High Cutoff	2	0	0.6663	0.385-0.947	
NA	2	0	0.399	0.129-0.668	
Region					0.0223
Europe	2	0	0.2667	0.094-0.438	
Asia	7	57.1	0.5341	0.382-0.686	

D. Overall Survival (OS)

This meta-analysis of 10 studies in figure 3 examining the association between androgen receptor (AR) expression and overall survival (OS) in TNBC reveals important findings with notable heterogeneity among the included studies. The random-effects model yielded a pooled hazard ratio of 0.80 (95% CI: 0.59-1.02), indicating a non-significant trend toward improved survival with AR expression. Most studies reported HRs greater than 1, though the estimates vary widely. Only Castellano (HR = 0.46, 95% CI: 0.25–0.67) shows a statistically significant protective effect, as its confidence interval does not cross 1. The analysis demonstrated moderate heterogeneity ($I^2 = 51.68\%$, $p = 0.0192$; $\tau^2 = 0.0418$; $Q = 19.80$), suggesting substantial variability in effect sizes across studies.

Fig. 3 Forest plot for association of AR expression in overall survival of TNBC

E. Publication Bias

Funnel plots and Egger’s regression tests were employed to evaluate potential publication bias in the meta-analysis. For DFS, the funnel plot demonstrated symmetrical distribution of studies, supported by a non-significant Egger’s test ($p = 0.06$), suggesting no substantial publication bias shown in Figure 4. In contrast, the overall survival (OS) analysis revealed asymmetry in the funnel plot, corroborated by a statistically significant Egger’s test ($p = 0.0346$), indicating potential publication bias depicts in Figure 5.

Fig. 4 Funnel plot assessing publication bias for DFS Studies

Fig. 5 Funnel plot revealing potential publication bias in OS studies

IV. CONCLUSION

This systematic review and meta-analysis explored the prognostic value of AR expression in TNBC, uncovering important insights into its relationship with patient outcomes. Although AR expression was not found to significantly affect overall survival, it showed a possible protective role in Disease-Free Survival, especially when considering differences across geographic regions. The variability observed among studies reflects both biological differences and inconsistencies in how AR is measured, with regional factors playing a notable role in disease-free survival outcomes. Importantly, the analysis found no evidence of publication bias in the DFS results. Overall, the study highlights the need for standardized methods to assess AR and point to the importance of considering population-specific factors when evaluating prognostic biomarkers. This review lays a strong foundation for future research to better understand the potential role of AR in guiding treatment and understanding the progression of TNBC.

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